

The Application of Nursery rhymes in Teaching Chinese as a Foreign Language

Zhang Jie¹, Wei Yanfeng², Md Jais Ismail³

College of Creative Arts, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Shah Alam, Malaysia

International exchange school, Nanchang Institute of Technology, JiangXi Province, China

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Abstract: Traditional mandarin nursery rhymes have characteristics that cannot be compared with other literary forms, so using them in mandarin learning can promote learners' communicative ability. Since the words of traditional Mandarin nursery rhymes contain actual language used, they provide learners with the opportunity to be exposed to the target language naturally. In this environment of natural contact, learners can learn Mandarin happily and comfortably, learn Mandarin effectively, and reduce the burden of Mandarin learning. Therefore, if the traditional Mandarin nursery rhymes are used properly for learning, they can be applied to the actual field of Mandarin education, and it will be possible to effectively guide students.

Keyword: Nursery Rhyme, Chinese language, Music, Second language, Rhyme, Rhythm.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of songs in foreign language learning has been shown in several studies to be efficient and successful in promoting language learning. The link between music and language in the process of acquiring and enhancing language, as well as what is more useful to utilize music in language learning, shall be examined before investigating educational techniques employing Mandarin Nursery Rhyme in Chinese language education.

II. MAJOR FORMAT GUIDELINES

A. music and language acquisition

Music and language development are inextricably linked. One of the actively used ways is using music to learn a second language under the supervision of the native language, and a foreign language. Music promotes language learning and development in a variety of ways (Trinick, 2011), including vocabulary, grammar and expression, reading, pronunciation, and writing. It also reduces learners' anxiety about learning, encourages them to concentrate, and builds their confidence. As a result, strategies for incorporating music into language or foreign language education are already in use in many languages.

According to Binti and Rashid, language proficiency is prioritized for learning a second language, and a restricted vocabulary prevents second language learners from speaking with native speakers. (Binti and Rashid, 2018) It is critical to create strategies to improve language recollection in order to efficiently learn a second language, as language knowledge is determined by language memory. Listening to music activates a network of brain regions involved with semantic processing and memory. Studies on the relationship between music and memory have revealed exactly how much activities help memory. (Loukas et al., 2021). Wallace discovered that the song's rhythmic pattern promotes recall of the words, which he discovered had an effect akin to memorizing when the melody was quickly and easily remembered, and claimed musical accompaniment aids recall vocabulary (McElhinney, M., Annett, 1996).

Krashen contends that even if the learning input is appropriate, learning motivation, confidence, and emotional state may each be variable, which might result in the onset of psychological ailments and ineffective knowledge absorption, which could hinder learning (Lichtman et al., 2021). Therefore, it is thought that a learner's own attitudes and emotions influence how much of the language they pick up from the environment, and that learners who are psychologically anxious, afraid, or lacking in confidence have much more limitations in language acquisition than learners who are not.

There are benefits to using music to acquire vocabulary, grammar, and expression, as well as listening, reading, writing, speaking, reading comprehension, and pronunciation (Ismail et al., 2022). According to Eren and Altay (2012), music training greatly encourages language acquisition in reading fluency, phonological awareness, language, and pronunciation of second languages for both children and adults. Using Mandarin Nursery Rhyme and chants while learning pronunciation in a second language also helps students get better at the skill so they can speak fluently with the accent of the language they wish to learn.

Using music in the language learning area may relieve stress, bring enjoyment, and develop language abilities all at the same time (Ismail et al., 2021). Singing may be used to improve language awareness for targeted second language acquisition as well as cultural learning. Learners participate in the process of learning by listening to and singing along with the song, as well as comprehending how each sound is joined to produce a sound and spoken (Ludke, Karen. 2008) Understanding the expressive process and purpose of language also helps students to acquire insight into how it works. Language learners benefit from exposure to numerous phonetic principles such as intonation, softening, assimilation, stress, tone reduction, and deletion through repetition and imitation of songs and lyrics, as well as the ability to approach them naturally through speaking and pronunciation practice (Mora, 2000). Musical style and substance are phenomena that reflect certain civilizations and ideologies. As a result, using songs may be a strong and beneficial learning strategy for developing a convergent Chinese language learning program in which language and culture function in tandem.

B. What is Chinese Nursery Rhyme ?

There are nursery rhymes in every country and nation in the world, and there are also nursery rhymes without words. Almost every child grows up with the accompaniment of nursery rhymes from birth. It can be said that nursery rhymes are children's childhood mentors, game partners, the beginning of art, and the enlightenment of life.

Nursery rhymes are the earliest literary form that Chinese people come into contact with in this world, and it accompanies the growth of Chinese people. These Nursery rhymes are short and clear, with strong local characteristics, humorous, harmonious syllables. Such as:

“小白兔，白又白，两只耳朵竖起来，爱吃萝卜爱吃菜，蹦蹦跳跳真可爱。”

"Little white rabbit, white and white, with two ears standing up to rice, loves to eat radishes and vegetables, and it's so cute to dance."

“小皮球，香蕉梨，马兰开会二十一，二五六，二五七，二八二九二十一。”

"Small balls, vanilla pears, Malaysia meeting twenty-one, two five six, two five seven, two eight two nine twenty one."

“黄鸡婆，背驮驮，三岁仔仔会唱歌，不是爷娘告诉我，自己聪明学到的。”

"The yellow rooster, she trains a horse, and her three-year-old Bozai can sing. It wasn't my parents who told me that Bai learned it by himself."

Then what are Chinese nursery rhymes? In Modern Chinese Dictionary, nursery rhymes are defined as "songs popular among children, with a relatively short form." Traditional nursery rhymes are one of folk literature, contained in folk songs. There are basically no clear categories and boundaries for nursery rhymes. All folk songs that are suitable for children to listen to and sing can be called nursery rhymes. Of course, the authors of nursery rhymes are not children, some are written by adults for children, and some belong to adults, but later become active in children's mouths because children are willing to accept and imitate them. Mr. Zhou Zuoren once said: "The author of children's songs, the lyrics of children's songs, and the ancient nursery rhymes". (Wang Ke, 2008) Chinese nursery rhymes are short rhyme styles that are popular among the people. They are in line with children's psychological characteristics. Children are happy to hear them and recite them. Children's nursery rhymes are simple and easy to understand, full of fun, full of rhythm, and have the beauty of rhythm, melody, imagery and many other artistic qualities.

There have always been many theories about the relationship between the two concepts of "children's song" and "nursery rhymes". "The Book of Shi Jing(Classic of Poetry): "I am worried, I sing ballads." (《诗经<国风·魏风·园有桃>》：“心之忧矣，我歌且谣”) There is a note in HanShiZhang: "Singing with a tune is a song, and singing without a tune is a ballad." (《韩诗章句》：“有章曲曰歌,无章曲曰谣”。) Those without accompaniment are called songs, and those without accompaniment are called rhymes. "Shi Fuzhen (施福珍), a Taiwanese children's literature theorist, said: "Children's songs are different from common nursery rhymes. As the words imply, rhymes (谣) are read, poems (诗) are recited, and songs (歌) are sung. Nursery rhymes only have words to read, no tune to sing. Those with words and tunes can be called Children's songs and folk songs."

Of course, nursery rhymes have a broad sense and a narrow sense also. In a narrow sense, it refers to songs created by children themselves or by adults that meet children's ability to accept; in a broad sense, in addition to the above-mentioned songs, it also includes songs that adults teach children to sing, but their content is not understood and accepted by children.

The research object of this paper is the songs without melody that are suitable for foreign students learning Chinese. In this article, the author defines the research object of "nursery rhymes" as non-singing nursery rhyme recitations used in teaching Chinese as a foreign language, songs specially used for teaching Chinese as a second language, with short rhymes and lively and interesting contents, which can be composed to help Students learn Chinese songs.

C. Features of Mandarin Nursery Rhyme

In the thousands of years of historical inheritance, Chinese nursery rhymes have been polished and processed by generations of people consciously or unconsciously, and have formed ten special traditional art forms that are loved by children. There are many forms of classification of nursery rhymes. It is generally divided according to the art form of nursery rhymes: such as playing basket songs, game songs, counting songs, question-and-answer songs, tongue-twister and riddle songs.

1. Lullaby

Lullabies are also called lullaby songs, which belong to the "mother song". This is a short nursery Rhyme mainly sung to infants and young children by mothers or other relatives, and is used to hypnotize, teach, and recognize objects. For example: "Sleep": "Little red horse, sleep standing up, don't want to be patted or hugged by mother. Little goldfish, sleep with eyes open, not noisy at all, not noisy at all. Little baby, sleep lying down, close the small eyes, with a smile on your face."

《睡觉》：“小红马，站着睡觉，不要妈妈拍，不要妈妈抱。小金鱼，睁着眼睡觉，一点也不吵，一点也不闹。小宝宝，躺着睡觉，闭上小眼睛，脸上带着笑。”

2. Game song

Game songs are nursery rhymes that children sing along with certain game actions during games. Such as: Hebei nursery Rhyme "Patting the ball": "Small ball, banana pear, Malan blossom twenty-one. Two eight two five six, two eight two five seven, two eight two nine twenty one. Three eight three five six, three eight Three-five-seven, three-eight-three-nine-forty-one..." During the game, there are three groups of people, two of them pull rubber bands, one dances in the middle, and sings nursery rhymes while dancing. With the various changes in the stepping and jumping movements, the speed and punctuation of nursery rhymes also change accordingly. The rhythm of this kind are very distinctive, and the speed is generally faster.

河北童谣《拍皮球》：“小皮球，香蕉梨，马兰开花二十一。二八二五六，二八二五七，二八二九二十一。三八三五六，三八三五七，三八三九四十一。……”

3. Counting songs

Counting songs are nursery rhymes that are described in an image suitable for children's aesthetic psychology and skillfully train children's counting ability. For example: the traditional nursery Rhyme "Clap Song": "what's 1, stick is 1. what's 2, duck is 2. what's 3, ears is 3. what's 4, sailboat is 4. what's 5, hook is 5..." like this The number-sensitivity turns numbers into images, and turns abstraction into concrete. In addition to being able to produce math knowledge education, it also infiltrates a certain amount of ideological education.

传统童谣《拍手歌》：“1 什么 1，棍子 1。2 什么 2，鸭子 2。3 什么 3，耳朵 3。4 什么 4，帆船 4。5 什么 5，钩钩 5。……”

4. Quiz song

Question-and-answer songs refer to nursery rhymes that narrate things and reflect life in the form of one question and one answer or repeated questions and answers. For example, "Whose Ears": "Who has long ears and whose ears are short, whose ears cover the face? Donkey ears are long, horse ears are short, and elephant ears cover the face. Whose ears are pointed, whose ears are round, whose ears can hear far? Pigs have pointed ears, monkeys have round ears, and dogs have ears that can hear far." The characteristic of the quiz song is that it has questions and answers.

例如，《谁的耳朵》：“谁的耳朵谁的耳朵长，谁的耳朵短，谁的耳朵遮着脸？驴的耳朵长，马的耳朵短，象的耳朵遮着脸。谁的耳朵尖，谁的耳朵圆，谁的耳朵听得远？猪的耳朵尖，猴的耳朵圆，狗的耳朵听得远。”

5. Tongue twister

Tongue twister is a traditional language game in China. It is a nursery Rhyme that combines some consonants, initial, finals and tones that are easily confused into meaningful nursery rhymes, and is specially used to train children's pronunciation. For example, "Seven Kinds of Fruits on Seven Trees": "One, two, three, three, two, one, two, three, four, five, six, seven. Seven aunts pick fruits, and seven flower baskets in their hands. There are seven wefts on seven trees.", apples, peaches, pomegranates, persimmons, plums, chestnuts, and pears." In short, tongue-twisting focuses on the training of initials, finals, and tones, and gathers words with the same or similar pronunciation together, requiring fast reading, so the reading makes people feel a strong sense of rhythm and wit.

《七棵树上结七样儿》：“一二三，三二一，一二三四五六七。七个阿姨米摘果，七个花篮儿手中提。七棵树上结七样儿，苹果、桃儿、石榴、柿子，李子、栗子、梨。”

6. Riddle Song

Riddle songs use allegorical methods to grasp a certain connection between the answers and the faces of the riddles, and describe the characteristics of phenomena or things in the form of rhyme. Such as "Dragonfly": "The teeth are like iron nails, the eyes are like stars, the wings are like gauze, and the long legs can't run." Riddle songs are interesting and beneficial intellectual games that can educate students about knowledge. At the same time, accurate and vivid language and interesting descriptions are conducive to the development of students' language.

《蜻蜓》：“牙体像铁钉，眼睛像星星，翅膀像轻纱，长脚不会跑。”

Therefore the features in Chinese mandarin nursery rhyme could be summarized: First, the unique characteristics of Mandarin Nursery Rhyme are that the vocabulary used in Mandarin Nursery Rhyme is not difficult, the rhythm is clear, the Rhyme is short, and it is suitable for expressing children's psychology. Second, Mandarin Nursery Rhyme are simple. Mandarin Nursery Rhyme are made of Chinese Traditional Nursery Rhyme, so they are basically made of vocabulary and expressions that are easy for children to sing and understand. The vocabulary of poetry used in Mandarin Nursery Rhyme has a pictorial or symbolic meaning. However, before grasping those meanings, it is basic to make the learner accept the emotions from the rhythm when reading or singing a traditional rhythm. Third, Mandarin Nursery Rhyme have structural characteristics of pitch and melody, which express the function of verbal communication in the form of dialogue. Therefore, continuous imitation and interactive conversational forms in Mandarin Nursery Rhyme work well for language development.

D. The music in Mandarin Nursery Rhyme

1, the rhyme in Mandarin Nursery Rhyme

When it comes to the music of nursery rhymes, the first thing we come into contact with is the "rhyme" of nursery rhymes, that is, rhyme and rhythm. Such as:

马兰开花二十一，二五六，二五七，二八二九三十一，三五六，三五七，三八 三九四十一……

Malan blossoms twenty one, two five six, two five seven, two eight two nine thirty one, three five six, three five seven, three eight Three nine forty one...

The entire nursery rhyme has no semantics, and what attracts children is the beauty of the "catchy" rhythm of the nursery rhyme. The cycle of "one" and "seven" with the same final vowel is like a drumbeat, coordinating the cheerful rhythm of children dancing rubber bands.

The so-called "rhyme" mainly refers to the vowel, and "rhyme" refers to the use of words with the same "rhyme" at the beginning, middle or end of certain sentences in rhymes or poetry ballads. An important means of sound beauty. Rhyme is the regular repetition of the same final. By rhyming, poems and ballads echo themselves in sound, such as:

摇摇摇 摇到外婆桥。

外婆叫我好宝宝, 糖一包, 果一包, 少吃滋味多, 多吃滋味少。

Shake Shake Shake to Grandma Bridge.

Grandma called me a good baby, one pack of sugar, one pack of fruit, eat less taste more, eat more taste less.

This ballad rhymes with "ao", and "bao(宝)" and "bao(包)" appear repeatedly at the end of the verses according to the law, forming a rhyme and at the same time creating a rhythm, which makes people predict the next sentence when reading the previous sentence, and read the following sentence. Recalling the previous sentence during a sentence, unintentionally but just rightly organized the scattered words into a whole. Due to the generation and transmission of folk oral creation and transmission, as well as the physiological, psychological and aesthetic characteristics of the subject children Influenced by factors such as interest, the rhyme of nursery rhymes shows a unique pattern and artistic personality.

2, the rhythm in Mandarin Nursery Rhyme

Three-character, four-character, five-character, and seven-character characters are frequently used in nursery rhymes with orderly sentences. The nursery rhymes written in the three-character style contain the fewest sentences among those written in the conventional manner. The three-character style has a short sentence structure, simple phrases, and a powerful rhythm. The easiest and most receptive users are kids. Such as 《吹喇叭》 (Small trumpet) :

小/喇叭, 滴滴/答, 吹支/歌, 送/娃娃。小/娃娃, 笑/哈哈, 嘟起/嘴, 亲亲/它。

Small trumpet, tick-tock, blow a song, send a doll. The little doll laughed, pouted, and kissed it.

In this nursery rhyme, there are eight three-character sentences, and there are pauses in the middle, neat and harmonious, and the reading is short and powerful, with a strong sense of rhythm. The sentences here are a bit like the footsteps in English poetry. They are pure and natural phonetic sentences rather than semantic sentences, that is, they are paused according to the pronunciation of nursery rhymes rather than semantics.

The four-character nursery rhymes are very neat and clear, and they are concise, powerful and catchy when read. Such as 《小鹿》 (Little deer) :

小鹿/小鹿, 毛衣/毛裤, 身上/开花, 头上/长树。

Little deer, sweater and woolen trousers, flowers on the body, trees growing on the head.

This seven-sentence four-syllable nursery rhyme forms a two-two uniform sentence pattern and produces a neat rhythm.

Except for a few three-character and four-character nursery rhymes, five-character and seven-character nursery rhymes appear the most among the three-character nursery rhymes. The main reason for this is that the five- and seven-syllable sentence patterns are relatively flexible. They often form two-two-one or two-one-two, two-two-two-one or four-three sentence pattern, and the combination of single and double syllables makes the The nursery rhymes are recited in a cadence, which is more beautiful. Such as "Going up the Mountain to Fight Tigers" :

一二三四五, 上山/打老虎。老虎/没打到, 打到/小松鼠。

松鼠/有几只?让我/数一数。 数来/又数去,一二三四五。

One, two, three, four, five, go up the mountain to fight tigers. The tiger missed, but the little squirrel was hit. How many squirrels are there? Let me count them. Counting and counting, one two three four five.

This nursery rhyme is also a pure phonetic sentence structure, with a rhythm of two or three, neat and clear, coupled with the foot rhyme of even-numbered sentences. When singing, it not only highlights the ending words, but also deliberately prolongs its syllables. It is lively, natural and full of charm. Such as "Counting Frogs":

一只青蛙/一张嘴, 两只眼睛/四条腿, 扑通一声/跳下水。

A frog with one mouth, two eyes and four legs jumped into the water with a plop.

The sentence structure of this song is also very neat, the rhythm of four and three is regular but not rigid, the number of sentences is relatively large but it is not difficult to recite, the well-proportioned and simple rhythm coupled with the vivid language reflects the playful color of nursery rhymes.

For the nursery rhymes mentioned above, the sentences in each nursery rhyme have a fixed sentence structure, regular and well-proportioned rhythm, and certain rules. The recitation is concise and clear, catchy and easy for children to recite. On the other hand, this kind of nursery rhyme should not be too long. If it is too long, it will easily create a monotonous feeling. Therefore, except for special nursery rhymes such as chain tones and tongue twisters, the length of Chinese nursery rhymes is relatively small.

E. Effect of integrating nursery rhymes into language learning

Nursery rhymes are an integral part of folk literature, which have accompanied and recorded history since primitive society. The development of many national or national literature is closely related to their national songs. After a long period of folk circulation, nursery rhymes are refined and clear, with harmonious rhymes and poetic charm.

The language proficiency, language expression skills or ideological content selected for mandarin education must be in line with the level of the learners. In the primary stage of learning Mandarin, language learning incorporating nursery rhymes can not only learn the pronunciation of Mandarin, but also easily learn vocabulary through repetition. In addition, traditional Mandarin nursery rhymes have been verified as works with many interesting basic Mandarin words and teaching lessons, and are helpful for foreign learners to have interesting exposure to Mandarin language and culture. The effect of learning Mandarin through traditional Mandarin nursery rhymes is as follows.

If Mandarin nursery rhymes are used as teaching materials, learners can participate even if they have a learning burden and will not feel bored. The research on the educational value and influence of mandarin nursery rhymes in mandarin education is summarized and presented as follows.

First, Mandarin lessons using Mandarin nursery rhymes can increase learners' motivation, engagement, and attention, and stimulate interest in the classroom. The more fear and anxiety learners have about learning and the classroom, the lower their academic motivation and achievement. As a way to solve this problem, Mandarin nursery rhymes can relieve the burden and fear of beginners in learning Mandarin, and learn the pronunciation, vocabulary and sentence patterns of Mandarin in a natural and comfortable atmosphere. In addition, it can also change the atmosphere by actively inducing learners' participation, interest, and concentration, and induce a good learning atmosphere emotionally, which has the psychological effect of relieving boredom in class.

Second, the lyrics of Mandarin nursery rhymes are short, easy to understand, with a clear sense of rhythm, and the melody is simple and repetitive, helping learners to memorize and understand in a short time. The language fun and rhythm in the vocabulary are easy to read with Mandarin nursery rhymes and provide fun. The meaning of Mandarin nursery rhymes is simpler than its meaning, and the repetitive characteristics of Mandarin nursery rhymes make it easy to remember even if students don't know the meaning of the lyrics, reduce the burden of memory, and help language development through natural reading.

Third, through traditional Chinese nursery rhymes, learners can come into contact with and acquire idioms of various expressions that are used in real life and are close to the essence of communication, which is different from the classroom language centered on textbooks. Mandarin speech can express a person's mood and emotions, and a lot of specific and

repetitive expressions are used. There are also many informal expressions, and the connection between the situation and the scene is very high. Mandarin nursery rhymes not only have a variety of expressions in idioms, but also have the characteristics of multi-purpose. Therefore, learners can access and acquire vocabulary used in real life that is close to the essence of communication, which is different from classroom language centered on textbooks.

Fourth, the vocabulary contained in nursery rhymes has symbolic meaning and metaphorical expression, which helps to enhance literary emotion. Poetry in general can be difficult for beginners because it is written, implied, and contains inner meaning. However, even though Mandarin nursery rhymes contain symbolic meanings and figurative expressions, they are composed of simple words, so the meaning of traditional Chinese nursery rhymes can be easily grasped. In this sense, Mandarin nursery rhymes play a guiding role in appreciating literary works.

Fifth, when learners sing Mandarin nursery rhymes in class, they can feel familiar with the target language they want to learn, and can arouse memory while reviewing what they have learned. Most importantly, learners will be able to understand the meaning of words and the stylistic meaning of the sentences they make by reading, listening to and repeating the lyrics of Mandarin nursery rhymes many times and fully assimilate them as their own.

Seventh, language and cultural learning can be conducted integrally using Chinese Traditional Nursery Rhyme. Language and culture are closely related, so learning a language is like learning the culture of a target language together. When learning a target language, it is important for foreign learners to learn and use appropriate expressions that can form a social and cultural consensus by understanding the culture of the country. Mandarin Nursery Rhyme were made up of everyday languages that were easy to understand and sympathize with various cultural factors such as Mandarin s' lives, thoughts, emotions, and lifestyles. Therefore, it can be used as a useful learning tool and medium for learners to understand and indirectly experience Mandarin culture as well as communication education such as speaking, listening, reading, and writing, vocabulary and sentence education, and grammar expression.

Eighth, Mandarin nursery rhymes have value as living language materials. It is not artificially processed language data, but vivid language data widely used in real life. It can be seen that it reflects many cultural elements such as Mandarin daily life, living habits, customs, emotions, and many other ways of expression in Mandarin.

Ninth, you can also use the "game" and "dynamic" elements contained in traditional Chinese nursery rhymes to learn cultural exchanges, which can cultivate new perspectives, thinking and cooperation. Many traditional Chinese nursery rhymes, including games and dances, are expected to be easy to use in teaching Chinese as a foreign language because they can increase the sense of intimacy among participating learners and help them communicate with each other.

In this way, mandarin nursery rhymes have the educational value of language. In terms of language, natural vocabulary learning and linkage learning of the four functions of language are possible, while the repetitive nature of Mandarin nursery rhymes is conducive to memory and understanding learning, and culture can be learned. By definition, it has the positive effect of alleviating classroom tension and reducing learning fears or burdens. It can also bring the joy and emotional stability that music brings. It has educational value as learners gain an integrated study of physical sensory, social and cultural, cognitive development and phonological elements.

F. Examples of Chinese Classroom Incorporating Nursery rhymes

1, Tonal and Pronunciation Learning

Since Chinese characters are ideographic characters, the other party can accurately understand Chinese characters only if the pronunciation pays attention to the intonation. Therefore, for first-time language learners, intonation and pronunciation practice are one of the important elements of learning.

Especially for vocal exercises, it is difficult for beginners to use rhythm to learn, so simple and repetitive tongue twisters can be used.

十是十，四是四。十四是十四，四十是四十。十四不是四十，四十也不是十四。

Practice noting the tones of ten (shí) and 是 (shì), which are final sounds, and the pronunciation of 4 (sì), which is a front syllable. For learners, all the words are unfamiliar pronunciations, but they are often encountered words, so try to memorize them and teach them to pronounce them quickly. Additionally, pitch changes must be explained to learners. Pitch changes only happen in special cases.

2, vocabulary learning

Vocabulary is the most important thing to know when communicating with others. Songs are easy to learn because various vocabulary is expressed in lyrics, and memorization is easy because they are sung repeatedly. Therefore, among these vocabularies, various vocabulary utilization methods using nouns, verbs, adjectives, directional verbs, seasons, dates, and onomatopoeia, which are basic elements that compose sentences, are presented.

爸爸的爸爸叫什么, 爸爸的爸爸叫爷爷

爸爸的妈妈叫什么, 爸爸的妈妈叫奶奶

妈妈的爸爸叫什么, 妈妈的爸爸叫外公

妈妈的妈妈叫什么, 妈妈的妈妈叫外婆

what's daddy's daddy's daddy's daddy's daddy's grandpa

What is the name of father's mother? What is the name of father's mother?

What is the name of mother's father? What is the name of mother's father?

What is mom's mother's name? Mom's mother's name is grandma

The vocabulary that learners encounter a lot in the early stages of learning Chinese is the name of a family member.

In this song, students can learn the member's title through family introduction, and at the same time, students can learn it as a personal pronoun.

The interjection in a song expresses the speaker's emotion, such as surprise, feeling, or response. Interjections are never combined with other words and are always used alone. A good understanding of exclamations can help you understand the situation or understand the other person's feelings.

两个小娃娃呀, 正在打电话呀。

“喂,喂,喂, 你在哪里呀?”

“哎, 哎, 哎, 我在幼儿园。”

两个小娃娃呀, 正在打电话呀。

“喂,喂,喂, 你在做什么?”

“哎, 哎, 哎, 我在学唱歌。”

Two little dolls are on the phone.

"Hello, hello, where are you?"

"Hey, hey, hey, I'm in kindergarten."

Two little dolls are on the phone.

"Hey, hello, hello, what are you doing?"

"Hey, hey, hey, I'm learning to sing."

3, Sentence Learning

The lyrics in children's songs are not made up of simple vocabulary lists. There are various ways to utilize Chinese sentence patterns, and students can learn the correct grammatical system through sentence pattern learning. If students use the method in sentence pattern learning based on the vocabulary they have used before, it will be of great help to students of Chinese language learning in everyday life as well as more natural sentence expression.

《谁的尾巴最好看》

谁的尾巴长呀；

谁的尾巴短；

谁的尾巴好像一把伞；

猴子尾巴长呀；

兔子尾巴短；

小松鼠的尾巴好像一把伞；

"Who Has the Best Tail"

whose tail is long;

whose tail is short;

whose tail is like an umbrella;

The monkey has a long tail;

rabbit tail short;

The little squirrel's tail is like an umbrella;

4, Learn culture and proverbs

《十二月歌》

正月新春舞龙灯，

二月郊外放风筝，

三月清明杨柳绿，

四月牡丹花正红，

五月端午赛龙舟，

六月荷花满池塘，

七月牛郎会织女，

八月中秋桂花香，

九月登高过重阳，

十月满园橘子黄，

冬月大雪压青松，

腊月梅花傲冰霜。

"December Song"

New Year's Day Dragon Lantern Dance,

Flying a kite in the suburbs in February,

March Qingming willow green,

April peonies are red,

Dragon boat races on the Dragon Boat Festival in May,

In June, the pond is full of lotus flowers,

Cowherd meets Weaver Girl in July,

Mid-autumn osmanthus fragrance,

September ascends over the Chongyang Festival,

October is full of oranges,

The winter moon is snowing heavily on the green pines,

The plum blossoms in the twelfth lunar month are proud of the frost.

Learn Chinese culture in daily life, share Chinese consciousness in history, which could let students speak Chinese better (Xian & Ismail, 2022). The twelve months of the Chinese people include many traditional folk activities, from natural phenomena, agricultural production, ceremonial folk customs, solar term diet and health care. Twelve-month nursery rhymes are Chinese people's understanding of the season and climate of the year by observing the annual movement of the sun. The knowledge system and social practice formed by the changing laws of phenology are the time system created by Chinese ancestors in the long-term agricultural production according to the laws of heaven and earth and climate change. It condenses the ecological wisdom of adapting measures to current conditions, adapting measures to local conditions, and circular development. By learning Twelve-month nursery rhymes, let students understand the Chinese ecological thought of "harmony between man and nature".

G. Note of Using nursery rhymes

The selection criteria for the following nursery rhymes are formulated with the educational goal of cultivating students' Chinese communicative ability and the practical functions of communication.

- 1, Simple and repetitive, so learners choose a song they can remember.
- 2, The content of the lyrics is colloquial, so learners choose an easy-to-learn song.
- 3, Even if the content of the lyrics does not necessarily contain educational content, we are looking for materials that are helpful for learning in terms of pronunciation, intonation, and vocabulary.
- 4, Among the languages used by many ethnic minorities in China, the lyrics of standard Chinese are selected.

The nursery rhymes are selected according to the main criteria mentioned above, and by using these nursery rhymes, they are able to arouse more interest of the learners and increase the concentration of the class.

III. CONCLUSION

Both music and language are expressive communication systems built on the basis of various basic elements of sound. As far as their basic attributes are concerned, they are the perception, production and communication capabilities of a sound system that are unique to humans and universally possessed by humans. The distinctive rhythm of the rhyme art of Chinese nursery rhymes, in addition to the distinctive rhythm produced by the regular alternation of the strength, length, and severity of the voice, another important expression is rhyme, which is of great significance to Chinese nursery rhymes, and it can make the sentences more melodious Beautiful, echoing back and forth, forming a perfect whole, obtaining a bright and comfortable auditory effect, easy to listen to and sing. The goal of Chinese language education for foreigners is to improve communication skills in Chinese. In order to improve the communication ability of Chinese language teaching, this study tries to combine nursery rhymes with learning as part of the teaching and learning of language-centered education and

culture-centered education. The reason for this is that the learning of nursery rhymes can stimulate learners' motivation and interest, not only learning pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar and other language materials, but also learning the four language functions of listening, speaking, reading and writing and cultural learning. But so far, there are very few studies on the use of nursery rhymes in the classroom of Chinese as a foreign language. Therefore, this study focuses on foreigners who learn Chinese as a second foreign language, and puts forward a preliminary discussion on the use of nursery rhymes in Chinese language education.

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